

CULTURAL HERITAGE AND ITS IMPORTANCE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM

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Abstract. *This article is aimed at studying the importance of cultural heritage in the development of tourism. During the study, various sources of information were used, and the most necessary materials were selected from them. These are resources related to the development of the tourism sector, what and how affects its development, and why the tourism sector is important in the development of countries, and also take into account the entertainment that should and is included in the tourism sector and its significance. The result of this study showed that the tourism sector has a huge impact on the economic side of the country, both in developing countries and in developed countries. Moreover, it also helps those countries that have natural resource deficiencies as well as unemployment problems. Also included is the proportional ratio of spending on the restoration of cultural heritage and the satisfaction of tourists with hotels. This article can be used to develop strategies for the development of cultural heritage, as well as to contribute to the importance of their preservation.*

Key words: *cultural heritage, restoration of monuments, importance of tourism industry, exchange culture, cultural tradition, economic growth.*

Аннотация. *Цель данной статьи- изучение важности культурного наследия в развитии сферы туризма. Во время изучения были использованы огромное количество источников информации и были отобраны самые необходимые. Большинство из них связанные с развитием туристического сектора , что и как влияет на его развитие и почему сфера туризма так важна для многих стран. Более того, были учтены развлечения такие как; фестивали, праздники, зоны отдыха и т.д. которые должны входить в состав туризма. Результаты исследования показали , что туристическая сфера оказывает огромное влияние на экономику страны как в развивающихся так и в развитых странах. Кроме того она помогает многим государствам, испытывающим нехватку природных ресурсов и проблемы с безработицей. Данная статья также рассматривает соотношение расходов на восстановление объектов культурного наследия и степень удовлетворенности туристов от пребывания в отелях. Этот материал может быть использован при разработке стратегий культурного наследия , а также способствует осознанию важности его сохранения.*

Ключевые слова: *Культурное наследие, реставрация памятников, значение туристической индустрии, обмен культурами, культурные традиции, экономический рост.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolaning maqsadi turizmni rivojlantirishda madaniy merosning ahamiyatini o'rganishdir. Tadqiqot davomida juda ko'p ma'lumot manbalaridan foydalanildi va eng keraklilari tanlab olindi. Ularning aksariyati turizm sohasining rivojlanishi, uning rivojlanishiga nima va qanday ta'sir ko'rsatishi va nima uchun turizm sohasi ko'plab mamlakatlar uchun juda muhim ekanligi bilan bog'liq. Bundan tashqari, o'yin-kulgilar, masalan; turizmga*

kiritilishi kerak bo'lgan festivallar, bayramlar, dam olish joylari va boshqalar. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatdiki, turizm sohasi ham rivojlanayotgan, ham rivojlangan mamlakatlar iqtisodiyotiga katta ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Bundan tashqari, u tabiiy resurslar tanqisligi va ishsizlik bilan bog'liq muammolarni boshdan kechirayotgan ko'plab mamlakatlarga yordam beradi. Ushbu maqola, shuningdek, madaniy meros ob'ektlarini tiklash xarajatlari va ularning mehmonxonalarda qolishidan turistlarning qoniqish darajasi o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikni o'rganadi. Ushbu materialdan madaniy meros strategiyalarini ishlab chiqishda foydalanish mumkin, shuningdek, uni asrab-avaylash muhimligi haqida xabardorlikka yordam beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: *Madaniy meros, yodgorliklarni ta'mirlash, turizm industriyasining ahamiyati, madaniyatlar almashinuvi, madaniy an'analar, iqtisodiy o'sish.*

Introduction

Nowadays, each of us understands that tourism has huge i in the development of the state. It contributes to the restoration and protection of historical, architectural and cultural sites, as well as the traditions and customs of each nation. Of course, most historical buildings such as monuments, architecture, and archaeological finds require restoration and maintenance. Consequently, the development of the tourism sector makes it possible to attract investment in the restoration of these objects, as they become attractive to their visitors. In addition, tourism contributes to the preservation of cultural traditions and customs. Each country, realizing the interest of tourists in their culture, begins to more actively preserve its traditions and present them to tourists. This may include organizing exhibitions or festivals, workshops and other events that help preserve and pass on unique aspects of culture from one generation to the next. A huge number of travelers, visiting various places, get the opportunity to learn about the history, art, architecture and traditions of this people. This helps them broaden their horizons and helps them better understand and respect other traditions and customs. After all, already in ancient times, people traveled to trade and exchange culture and knowledge. And it has contributed to the strengthening of ties between people from different cultures and countries. Meeting new people, exchanging experiences and ideas has helped and continues to help broaden horizons and increase tolerance. In this article, I will cover topics related to the development of tourism and what exactly affects their promotion. First, there will be the impact of historical buildings on the tourism industry, then about what diversity can be included to attract a number of tourists.

Tourism and development

Tourism in the improvement of Uzbekistan is associated with the restoration and protection of cultural heritage and cultural objects. According to Farmonov E. A. "As we know, in the period of globalization, post-industrial civilization understands that the high potential of historical and cultural heritage is its preservation. development and effective use of key resources of the world economy" It is necessary to note to the fact that it is historical places that create the first impression of tourists, which leads to a rise in their number. According to G. Georgiev, "cultural heritage - both tangible and intangible in the era of the information society of modern times will play an ever-increasing role, because it is one of those means of life of mankind that carry memory, which will more and more attract the attention of ordinary people, as well as the tourism industry" Having observed some situation connected with influence of tourism in the economic growth we elicit that the number of tourist impact in the restore cultural heritage.

Figure1

The proportion of spending 75 billion soums on restoration in 2022

Note: This pie chart clearly shows the funds spent on the restoration of architectural buildings in several cities such as: Bukhara, Samarkand, Khorezm, Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya in 2022. It is worth noting 17 facilities in Bukhara, four each in Surkhandarya and Kashkadarya, five in the Khorezm region, and three in Samarkand.

Why tourism sector necessary for countries?

Of course, all over the world, the tourism sector is considered one of the most important resources of a country's income and influence on the country's development. Moreover, in many developing countries, the tourism sector has become one of the sources of international income exchange between countries, while even in developed countries, income from international tourism can make a significant contribution to the balance of payments and to travel in general. For example, we can take the United Kingdom: in 1998, its revenues from international tourism amounted to 12.7 billion pounds. It should be borne in mind that this amounted to only 4.6% of total exports. (British Tourism Authority (BTA), 2000). Tourism is already considered an effective source of income and employment opportunities for locals. Based on some information, it has already been noted about the global contribution of tourism to unemployment and GDP, and this is already considered the main source of unemployment for many countries. For example, for such a country, you can take Cyprus, more than 25% of the workforce is already involved in the tourism sector. It is worth noting that for countries that have restrictions on the industrial sector or a small amount of natural resources, dependence on international tourism can become the main source of income for the country. One such case is being considered in the country of the Gambia. This country lacks any resources, which indicates their dependence on the tourism sector.

The creation of new historical sites increases the interest of tourists.

The creation of new historical sites not only enriches the cultural heritage but also significantly increases tourist interest and attendance. According to Farmonov E. A.

“With the development of the tourism business in Uzbekistan, mainly in historical and ancient cities such as Bukhara, Samarkand, Khiva and Tashkent, new historically valuable areas and new cultural objects are emerging” It is worth paying attention to the fact that it is historical places that create the first impression of tourists, which leads to an increase in their number .

The organization of theatrical, creative parties various book fairs, libraries in the cities of Bukhara, Samarkand and Khiva gives a good result, raises the status of the people and the country. According to Xodjayeva .F.N. “For example, for tourists, sometimes local creative and literary monuments are less important, but they have their own tourist motives and attract the interest of amateurs. To do this, it is necessary to form a variety of tourist programs, theatrical scenes and routes for those interested in literary monuments or authors of books and treatises. Works of art can create an image of the culture of the visited country and have their own value, niche” Moreover, when tourists visit a certain country, they expect to see not only historical monuments but also relax and get some food for thought. According to Xodjayeva . F.N The musical and creative potential of the regions is an attractive element of culture. Festivals of national, classical and popular music gather thousands of participants every year. Therefore, it is desirable to hold various local national festivals such as sail, carnivals, mask shows, concerts in nature, folk festivals.

Tourists' perception of hotels

Without doubt, cultural heritage, historical buildings, festivals all attract tourists, which leads to an increase in their number year after year. However, it is worth taking into account other aspects of the tourism sector for each country, for example, the reception of tourists in hotels. Perhaps this is the most significant part of the trip, since the tourist should feel the maximum comfort, which depends on the service of the hotels. After conducting some research, we were able to divide their satisfaction from a given hotel into categories, as well as into a proportional ratio.

Figure 2

Average degree of client satisfaction from hotels

Note: The given pie chart clearly demonstrates the proportion of client satisfaction from hotels separating them in categories such as: comfort, room quality, language skills, sense of hospitality, extra charges quality, variety of hotels leisure facilities as well as professional skills.

Conclusion

In conclusion, I would like to note that the tourism sector plays a decisive role in the development of states and provides opportunities for economic growth. It is worth considering the fact that not only cultural heritage is important for the field of tourism and its improvement, but

also various exhibitions, master classes, exhibitions, festivals, etc. After all, all this will not only distract him from listening to the history of the country, from the guide, but also allow them to penetrate into this situation, feel and see it with their own eyes. Moreover, there is a possibility of new acquaintances with the locals. And it is also necessary to take into account their comfort and reception in our hotels, the tourist should feel the maximum comfort from this country and leave good impressions for himself.

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